

Improving WPT color image decomposition

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Abstract

Securing the confidential secret and personal messages is a vital and important task. In this paper we will show how to increase the security of LSB2 method of data steganography to protect the message imbedded in digital color image.

An encryption phase will be added to the hiding process, this encryption will be based on dividing the holding image into blocks and reordering the blocks to get the encrypted image, the reordering sequence here will be kept as a PK to decrypt the encrypted image.

Key words: Steganography, encryption, blocking factor, reordering table, PK, MSE, PSNR.

I- Introduction

Social media has spread recently, as it is now widely used in the circulation of various messages [1], [2], [3], [4]. Some of the messages in circulation are confidential or may be of a personal nature [49], [50], which requires their protection [51], [52], [53] and preventing intruders from reading [23], [24], [25] or understanding them by hiding or encrypting them [46], [47], [48].

The digital color image is considered one of the most important types of digital data used to carry and hide private messages [5], [6], [7], for several reasons, the most important of which are: easy access to the image, ease of image processing, and the possession of a large size image that can hide short and long messages without affecting the digital image.

The digital color image is a three-dimensional matrix [1], [2] in which the first dimension is devoted to represent the red color [11], [12], [13]; the second dimension represents the green color, while the third dimension represents the blue color. Digital images are usually characterized by high resolution [14], [15], which means that the matrix is large and contains a huge number of pixels, which enables us to hide large text messages [16], [17].

To find out how clear the image is, we can use the histogram as shown in figure 1, where one trend is assigned to each color [18], [19]. Histogram [20], [21], [22] is a one column matrix of 256 elements, each element value points to the repetition of color (0 to 255), the three histograms can be added together to give use the image total histogram as shown in figure 2.

Figure 1: Color image and associated histograms

Figure 2: Image total histogram

II- Steganography and cryptography

Steganography is the art of hiding secret message in another holding or covering data, mainly color image [46], [47], [48]. The method of concealment shall be characterized by the following:

- Ease of implementation.
- The ability to fulfil messages of different sizes (short messages and long messages).
- That the concealment process does not significantly affect the image so that the observation result does not take place with the galaxy eye to prevent intruders from trying to process the image that carries the message [40], [41], [46].

- The method of concealment shall be safe [14], [15].

Many methods were introduced for message steganography [45], [48], [49], and the most widely used methods are based on least significant bit (LSB) method such as LSB2 method. LSB method of message hiding reserves 8 bytes from the covering image to hold one message character, thus the capacity of this method is equal to the image size divided by 8. LSB2 method of steganography reserves 4 bytes from the covering image to hold one character from the message, thus the capacity of LSB2 method equal the image size divided by 4, figure 3 shows how LSB and LSB2 act with the bits to hold the message characters.

Figure 3: LSB and LSB2 operation

Here in this paper we will use LSB2 method of data hiding because it has a higher capacity as shown in table 1:

Table 1: Capacities of LSB and LSB2

Image number	Size(byte)	Maximum message length(byte) using LSB	Maximum message length(byte) using LSB2
1	150849	18856	37712
2	77976	9747	19494
3	518400	64800	129600
4	5140800	642600	1285200
5	4326210	540776	1081552
6	122265	15283	30566
7	151353	18919	37838
8	1890000	236250	472500
9	6119256	764907	1529814
10	151875	18984	37968

LSB2 method has in noticeable effect [23], [24] on the holding image and the changes on the holding byte range from -3 to 3 as shown in table 2:

Table 2: Changes of the holding byte using LSB2 method

Original LSB2 bits	Holding LSB2 bits	Remark
00	00	No change
00	01	Add 1
00	10	Add 2
00	11	Add 3
01	00	Subtract 1
01	01	No change
01	10	Add 1
01	11	Add 2
10	00	Subtract 2
10	01	Subtract 1
10	10	No change
10	11	Add 1
11	00	Subtract 3
11	01	Subtract 2
11	10	Subtract 1
11	11	No change

LSB2 method provides the following advantages:

- ✓ High capacity.
- ✓ Easy to implement.
- ✓ Minor changes in the holding image, LSB2 provides a high value for peak-to-signal-noise ratio (PSNR), and low value for mean square error (MSE) between the original and the holding images, thus the changes in the image can not be noticed by a human eyes .

The disadvantage of LSB2 method is that it easy can be hacked (not secure), and to overcome this disadvantage we have to encrypt the holding image [11], [12], [13].

Encryption is the destruction of data [8], [9], [10] that becomes incomprehensible, and here many methods were introduced for encryption, and in our paper we will focus on blocking and reordering method of data encryption [25-45].

Encryption method must provide the following:

- ✓ Low value of PSNR between the original image and the encrypted one [31], [32].
- ✓ High value of MSE between the original image and the encrypted one [33], [34].
- ✓ High level of security by using a private key, which can not be hacked [35], [36].

III- The proposed method

The proposed method for secret message hiding will be implemented as follows:

Hiding process:

This phase can be implemented as shown in figure 4 applying the following tasks:

- 1) Message hiding:
In this task we shall select the message and the covering image, and then we have to apply LSB2 method to generate the holding image.
- 2) The holding image must be encrypted using blocking and reordering method: here we have to select the number of blocks (blocking factor); then we have to divide the holding image into equal blocks (as shown in table 3: here blocking factor equal 11), at the end we have to reorder the blocks to get the encrypted image (here the sequence of the reordering will be used as a PK).

Figure 4: Hiding diagram

Table 3: Reordering table for image 5

Block number	Size	Order(PK)
1	393291	7
2	393291	11
3	393291	9
4	393291	12
5	393291	6
6	393291	2
7	393291	4
8	393291	8
9	393291	3
10	393291	1
11	393291	5
12	9	10

Extracting process:

The extraction process as shown in figure 5 will be implemented applying the following tasks:

Figure 5: Message extracting diagram

- Decryption

Here we must have the PK (see table 4), this key can be used to reorder the image to get the decrypted image

Table 4: PK

Order(PK)
7
11
9
12
6
2
4
8
3

1
5
10

- Apply LSB2 to extract the message from the decrypted image.

IV- Implementation and experimental results

The proposed method was implemented using the images shown in table 1, figures 6, 7 and 8 shows the obtained outputs of using image 2 and the message " **May God protect Jordan and the Jordanians'** with length=41:

Figure 6: Covering image (example)

Figure 7: Holding image (example)

Figure 8: Encrypted holding image (example)

LSB2 method was applied using the smallest image in size, table 5 shows the experimental results, while table 6 shows the experimental results using bigger image.

Table 5: using the smallest image (image 2)

Message length	MSE	PSNR	Hiding time(second)
41	0.0062	161.6874	0.00001
82	0.0107	156.2165	0.0001
164	0.0205	149.6892	0.0020
328	0.0411	142.7390	0.0040
656	0.0810	135.9584	0.0060
1312	0.1631	128.9575	0.0120
2624	0.3243	122.0860	0.0250
5248	0.6503	115.1290	0.0730
Average	0.1622	139.0579	0.0153

Table 6: using the biggest image (image 9)

Message length	MSE	PSNR	Hiding time(second)
41	0.000055072	208.8940	0.0030
82	0.00011554	201.4845	0.0030
164	0.00024055	194.1510	0.0050
328	0.00050022	186.8298	0.0060
656	0.0010	179.7846	0.0080
1312	0.0020	173.1017	0.0140
2624	0.0040	165.9906	0.0270
5248	0.0081	158.9733	0.0530
Average	0.0020	183.6512	0.0149

From tables 5 and 6 we can see that using bigger images will enhance the parameter PSNR and MSE for LSB2.

The encryption phase must reduce the value of PSNR and increase the value of MSE; this was proved by the experimental results shown in table 7:

Table 7: Encryption result
Use message :'**May God protect Jordan and the Jordanians'** with length=41

Image number	Block size	MSE	PSNR	Encryption time
1	13713	13984	15.3689	0.000100
2	7088	4352.1	27.0410	0.000010
3	47127	8114.9	20.8107	0.0020
4	467345	8887.4	19.9014	0.0260
5	393291	8389.6	20.4777	0.0220
6	11115	5198.4	25.2642	0.0010
7	13759	9584.8	19.1460	0.000010
8	171818	11909	16.9744	0.0090
9	556296	3206.4	30.0962	0.0310
10	13806	15797	14.1496	0.0010
Average		8942.4	20.9230	0.0092

From table 7 we can see the following:

- Low PSNR value.
- High MSE value.
- The encryption process add significant small value to the hiding time (0.009 seconds in average);
- The same blocking factor and PK may be used for deferent images.

Conclusion

A method of improving the security of LSB2 method of secret message steganography was introduced.

The obtained experimental results showed that the proposed method satisfies the requirements of data encryption by decreasing the value of PSNR and decreasing the value of MSE. The method is secure because it uses a PK which is very difficult to guess and hack.

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